

ORGANIZATIONAL FORMS OF INNOVATION ACTIVITY MANAGEMENT IN INDUSTRIAL COMPANIES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7444704>

Abdullayeva M.N

Candidate of Economics, Associate Professor of TSTU

Egamberdiyev O.B

assistant of TSTU

Annotation: *In this paper, the organizational forms of innovation management in industrial companies are considered.*

Keywords: *Industrial enterprises, innovation activity, motivation, innovation culture*

The main objective of the implementation of industrial policy is to increase the competitiveness of domestic products and accelerate institutional and organizational changes based on the intensification of innovation and scientific and technical policy. One of the mechanisms for increasing the efficiency of using scientific developments and introducing the results of fundamental and applied research in industry can be the use of innovative potential.

In recent years, the concept of management has expanded as a result of the emergence of a new science of enterprise restructuring. The emergence of this direction is due to the process of structural reorganization of companies that began in the 90s, caused by the need to adapt their activities to permanent changes in the external environment.

Among the main areas of reorganization, there are three groups: the elimination of low-productivity structural units in order to increase production efficiency, as well as the improvement of the structure to facilitate the control function; creation of a strategically effective structure in the implementation of innovative strategies; introducing innovative organizational concepts as part of the dissemination of a new understanding of the organization.

The study of the innovative activities of many foreign companies allows us to distinguish three fundamentally distinctive organizational forms - sequential, parallel and integral.

□ the sequential form involves the phased implementation of innovative activities in turn in all functional units;

□ Parallel organization involves carrying out all the work on the project simultaneously in all departments;

□ an integral form of innovation management, which is often called the method of joint design.

When making the next innovative decision, the project manager creates target units, where specialists from various divisions of the company are invited for the duration of the project. At the same time, they are in double submission - to the project manager and the head of their unit. However, the conflict of subordination does not arise, since the functions of each leader are clearly separated. The project manager determines the tasks necessary to fulfill the decision of the top management, and the functional and line managers carry out the function of organization (distribution of duties) and control over the entire course of work.

At large foreign enterprises, such forms are often transformed into independent research and production complexes for the development of new business areas (for example, in IBM) or venture divisions if projects are assessed as high-risk. At the highest level of management, advisory task committees or councils are created to determine the company's scientific and technological development strategy, general research and innovation planning, which make recommendations to the board of directors and the president of the company. They are composed of highly professional consultants, often brought in from outside.

So, we can note the following trends in the reorganization of foreign companies in order to increase the efficiency of innovation:

- reduction of administrative levels of management and expansion of the managerial range;
- formation of multiple management structures, when, along with the main one, temporary secondary structures and separate coordinating subdivisions are created;
- use of such advantages of matrix structures as reduction of terms of work, increase of personal and collective responsibility, invitation of external consultants, absence of double bureaucratization as a result of a clear distribution of functions;
- Creation at the senior management level of standing committees for strategic advice to senior management;
- Consolidation of R&D, marketing, sales and production divisions into multifunctional research and production complexes for the development and implementation of innovations;
- organization within target groups of consumer centers for market testing of new products;
- empowering the head of project departments with the function of coordinating their activities and determining priority tasks for the project;

- establishment of a special motivation system focused on achieving the final result and creating an innovative culture in the company.

Thus, all this makes it possible to reduce resistance to the innovation process, reduce project implementation time, reduce the number of shortcomings in the execution of work, improve the quality of new products, enhance the effectiveness of the introduction of new marketing measures, and stimulate the growth of creative initiative.

REFERENCE:

1. Innovation management. Textbook / Ed. S.D.Ilyenkova, - M.: Unity, 1997
2. Popov D. Evolution of indicators of the enterprise development strategy// Management of the company. - M., 2003. - No. 2.